

Management of Character Education Based on Religious Culture in the Global Era: Case Study Al-Ghontory Elementary School Tulungagung, Indonesia

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Abstract:- The global era that is happening at this time brings the impact of changes in the lives of the world's people. This change can be seen in the behavior and perspective of the community towards ethical values that exist in everyday life. This paper aims to describe the management of character education based on religious culture in elementary schools. Learning character values can be carried out by forming a religious culture in schools. Religious culture can strengthen student behavior in carrying out character values in everyday life. This research was conducted at Al-Ghontory Elementary School Tulungagung, Indonesia. Data were taken by interview, observation, and documentation techniques. The results of the study indicate that character values can be implemented by strengthening the implementation of religious culture in schools. A good religious culture can realize the implementation of quality education, shape the attitudes, behavior, and morals of good students. Students are more disciplined and responsible in carrying out the learning process at school.

Keywords:- Management, Character Education, Religious Culture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global era that is happening at the moment is delivering the world community to use and utilize technology in various fields of life (Haryono, 2018). The progress of this technology is marked by the presence of intensive and massive automation applications in various fields of work to be digital (Haryono, 2018). The advancement of science and technology has brought the world community to reform and improve educational institutions so that they become quality and have competitiveness in preparing quality human resources. Quality human resources will be able to adapt to the progress that is happening at this time. Efforts are being made to improve human resources in several countries, including through education. Like the United States since 2001 has launched the program "No Child Left Behind" to catch up with the European countries (Dee & Jacob, 2011; Sclafani, 2002). Singapore reforms education by increasing the effectiveness of the education system from the school level to the national level which includes: education oriented to "The Goal of Broad-Based Education Outcomes", the curriculum is designed flexibly so that it can serve the needs

of students according to the level of intelligence, thinking skills, group work, project work, providing one computer for two students, all schools can access the internet, and there is an educational policy that supports the program.

The development of science and technology has a very significant influence on behavior and culture in a nation (Putit & Arnott, 2007). This condition also occurs in Indonesia, the Indonesian nation is faced with a crisis of character that is quite alarming among adolescents so that it tends to behave that is not in accordance with the values of the nation's character. Based on these situations and conditions, the Indonesian government issued a policy on a national curriculum that emphasized more on competency and character-based learning called the 2013 curriculum (Abidin, 2014; Sofyan & Komariah, 2016; Mutohar & Trisnantari, 2020). The implementation of education and learning that is happening at the moment also tends to develop cognitive aspects, while the soft skills or non-academic aspects as the main elements of character education have not been optimally considered. This condition is a challenge that must be faced by educational institutions in Indonesia in the success of national education goals.

Education in Indonesia is directed to educate the life of the nation, develop the potential of students to become human beings who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens (Sistem Pendidikan Nasional No 20 Tahun 2013). This shows that character education as a national policy must be realized starting from preschool education, basic education, secondary education, and higher education. This strategic policy must be responded well by schools to be able to participate in preparing young people and strong and qualified Indonesian human resources.

Schools as an educational institution have a culture that is formed and influenced by values, school policies, organizational member behavior, and habits practiced by members of the organization at school. School culture shows capabilities that are by the demands of learning in teaching students based on the values of characters taught in school (Mutohar & Trisnantari, 2020; Sumarni, 2017; Sutyitno, 2012). The character values that are the commitment of the school must be implemented well through education and learning and habituation programs in teaching students. This

habituation program is based on religious values that will be developed in schools in the learning system.

Religious culture is closely related to efforts to implement the values contained in the teachings of Islam to give birth to the commitment of all personnel in the school to carry out consistently and consistently (Nurcholih, 2019;). The implementation of religious values in schools can accustom students to be able to behave properly by religious teachings. Behavior that is implemented continuously can shape the character of students. This shows that habituation is a very important element in forming a good character for students in school. This explanation is also based on the results of research showing that religious culture implemented in schools influences in creating quality education, the formation of positive attitudes and morals for all personnel in schools (Hakim, 2012; Nurcholih, 2019). Such conditions are very supportive of achieving high learning achievement and character students.

Schools have a responsibility in teaching the values of character to students which include components of knowledge, awareness or willingness, and actions to carry out these values, both towards God Almighty, self, others, environment, and nationality so that they become human beings. us (Mutohar & Trisnantari, 2020). The implementation of character education must pay attention to the following educational components: curriculum content, learning process, assessment, relationship quality, handling or management of subjects, school management, implementation of co-curricular activities, empowering infrastructure, financing, and the performance of all citizens and the environment school.

Based on the results of the study explained that a person's success is not solely determined by knowledge and technical ability (hard skills), but also determined by the ability to manage themselves and others (soft skills). This research revealed success is only determined by about 20 percent by hard skills and the remaining 80 percent by soft skills. Even the most successful people in the world can succeed because more soft skills are supported than hard skills (Akbar, 2000). Therefore, the implementation of improving the quality of character education in schools must be strengthened so that national education goals can be achieved properly and can prepare Human Resources who have the competence and good character.

Creemers and Reynolds (2002) revealed the results of their research that: leadership has a role in creating organizational reality and shaping organizational culture. Organizational productivity includes teacher performance can be realized if it is supported by a strong organizational culture and a conducive organizational climate. The leadership style adopted by the principal will influence the formation of culture and organizational climate in the school. Likewise, DeRoche (1985) explains that organizational culture is one of the variables that also determines the success of work implementation. The research results of Gordon (1990), Creemers, and Reynolds (2002) show that a strong organizational culture makes members more satisfied, motivated, and committed. big

towards the organization. Likewise, Sergiovanni (1987) found that a strong culture would increase the commitment, enthusiasm, and loyalty of members towards the organization. From these results, it can be concluded that the strong and positive culture that exists in schools will be able to improve teacher performance because teachers have strong motivation, job satisfaction, and high commitment to the success of learning. Therefore, the strengthening of religious culture in schools must be considered and carried out as effectively as possible to be able to form schools that excel in academics and be able to produce outputs that are characterized by the values and teachings of Islam.

This research was conducted to obtain an in-depth picture of the management of the development of religious culture in shaping the character of students in schools. In connection with this matter, several problems were examined in this study. The intended problems are: (1) planning the development of religious culture in shaping student character, (2) a strategy for developing a religious culture in shaping a student's character, (3) an evaluation system for developing a religious culture in shaping a student's character. This problem is the focus of studies on the development of religious culture in schools. This is important to be implemented in improving the quality of schools and to provide patterns and colors of Islamic education institutions in schools by the core values developed in Islamic Education Institutions based on the vision and mission owned by the school.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study aims to examine the management of character education based on religious culture in the global era. The research method used is a combination research method with a sequential exploratory design (Cresswell, 2017; Sugioyono, 2017). The sequential exploratory design was carried out by collecting and analyzing qualitative data and followed by collecting quantitative data. Qualitative data were collected using in-depth interviews, participant observation, and documentation. The quantitative data was collected using a questionnaire answered by 80 students as the research sample with a population of 320 students starting in grades 4, 5, and 6 at Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School, Tulungagung, East Java, Indonesia. Samples were taken by proportional random sampling in grades 4,5, and 6 as research objects. Qualitative data analysis was carried out using interactive data analysis techniques starting from Data condensation, Data display, and Conclusion drawing/verification (Milles and Huberman, 2014). The quantitative data analysis used descriptive statistical techniques to determine the system of religious culture in shaping the character of students and strategies for strengthening religious culture in shaping the character of students in Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School.

The results of qualitative research are used as the basis for compiling research instruments on the system of religious cultural values in shaping students' character. This instrument has 8 indicators as follows: value of honesty, value of independence, achieving spirit, worship value, quality value, never give up, dare to try, and self-motivation.

As for the research instrument on the strategy of strengthening religious culture in shaping student character, there are 3 indicators as follows: commitment, communication, and continuous improvement. The data were analyzed by using a combine and interpret result technique based on the results of the study using a qualitative and quantitative approach. The findings of qualitative research and the results of descriptive hypothesis testing are used to conclude the final results of the study. The conclusions of the findings of this combination research will be discussed in depth so that it can bring up theoretical implications and practical implications that will become recommendations to be taken into consideration in the formation of student character based on strengthening religious culture in elementary schools.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

The school as an educational organization has its own culture that forms the style of a whole and a unique system. The specificity of religious culture in schools is inseparable from the vision, mission, and educational processes that take place within it which require all elements or components of

the school as an area of organizational work to be carried out properly. These elements interact with each other and reciprocally have links to each other, both artifacts and values, within the organization itself and with the external environment. The vision developed by the Al-Ghontory Elementary School Tulungagung is: "Fostering Students with Good Morals and Achievements."

The planning of religious values developed at Islamic Elementary School Tulungagung is closely related to efforts in fostering students so that they can behave well and excel. The aims and targets of education in Al-GhontoryIslamic Primary School are the formation of basic Islamic attitudes: (1) inculcation of faith in Allah (*aqidah akhlaq*), (2) habituation of Islamic culture (fond of worship, fond of learning, disciplined, creative, independent, clean and healthy life, and live the character values), and (3) mastery of basic knowledge and skills. These three things are the value system planned and agreed upon by the school to be developed in shaping the character of students in the Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School. These religious values can be explained in the form of pictures as follows:

Fig. 1: Religious Culture in the Formation of Student Character in Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School

The planning of planting *aqidah akhlaq* towards students of Islamic Elementary School was carried out in the whole learning process in the school. The cultivation of *aqidah akhlaq* is closely related to (1) basic knowledge of Faith, Islam, and Ihsan, (2) basic knowledge of praised and ignoble morality, (3) love of Allah and His Messenger, (4) pride in Islam and the spirit to fight for it in everyday life. The custom of Islamic culture developed at Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School is closely related to fond of worship, fond of learning, disciplined, creative, independent, clean and healthy living, and the implementation of Islamic customs or values developed in daily life. The love of worship must be instilled in children from an early age because in elementary schools it is very necessary to form a strong foundation of worship so that the values of worship can be actualized in daily life so that in subsequent developments it can be used as an inner control in the participants' socio-cultural life students.

The mastery of knowledge and skills developed at the Islamic Elementary School is closely related to knowledge of the subject matter of educational programs, knowing and skilled in daily worship, knowing and skilled in reading and writing the Qur'an, in simple understanding contents of the Al-Qur'an content and carry out in everyday life, integrated with education and learning programs in the Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School.

Islamic Elementary Schools have a value system developed in shaping effective school culture. Value is something that is recognized by people based on feeling as something neatly arranged, people can act on value by thinking, acknowledging, appreciating, and encouraging it. In the lives of individuals and society, values are the driving force and direction of individual and community behavior. The values taught in the Al-GhontoryIslamic elementary school are the value of honesty, the value of independence, the spirit of achievement, the value of worship, the value of quality, never give up, dare to try, and self-motivation.

These values become the core values of schools in shaping student character. The results of the analysis of the implementation of character values in the whole learning

process at school can be explained in the form of a table as follows:

Value System in Schools				
Indicator	Score			Criteria
	F	N	(%)	
Value of Honesty	71	80	89%	Very good
Value of Independence	60	80	75%	Good
Achieving Spirit	67	80	84%	Very good
Worship Value	70	80	88%	Very good
Quality Value	69	80	86%	Very good
Never give up	62	80	78%	Very good
Dare to try	65	80	81%	Very good
Self-motivation	66	80	83%	Very good
Average Total Score	530	640	83%	Very good

Table 1: The System of Religious Value in Forming the Character of Students at Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School

The value of honesty is taught to students in every learning process in school in order to foster students to become generators who have the character of the nation. Honesty is the foundation that must be had by students in carrying out the learning process in the Al-Ghontory Islamic elementary school. Based on the results of the study showed that the level of honesty of students is in very good condition, which is 89% of students are able to carry out the value of honesty well. The value of honesty that exists in yourself and in others is needed by every individual in his life. In order for students to be able to apply these values of honesty, the role of teachers and principals is very important to foster children, to be honest in all situations. In this case, the teacher always reminds and motivates students to always be honest.

The fostering and development of honesty values is an effort developed by schools to have a strong and positive culture in shaping the national character of students in schools so that it has implications for improving the quality of education. In this case, the Ministry of National Education (2007) explains that: the benefits obtained by developing a strong, intimate, conducive and responsible school culture and climate can: (1) guarantee a better quality of work, (2) open up the entire communication network from everything type and level of both vertical and horizontal communication, (3) more open and transparent, (4) create a high level of togetherness and belonging, (5) increase solidarity and a sense of kinship, (7) if finding mistakes will be corrected soon, (8) can adapt well to the development of science and technology.

Independence is one of the values taught at Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School. This independence is closely related to student learning activities and learning processes in schools. Independence is developed by the school to train children to be able to take responsibility, both for themselves and others. The forms of independence that students must have are: students can do school work independently. Based on the results of the study, it showed that the independence of students was in good condition,

namely 75% of students were able to carry out school assignments independently. Education and learning the value of independence to students in elementary schools has very important benefits in training and accustoming students to carry out their duties and responsibilities properly. The value of independence can also build student confidence in taking a strategic role in the learning process at school.

The spirit of achievement is a very important value in shaping the national character of students. Therefore students need to be motivated to always improve their academic and vocational achievements so they have life skills. This achievement will also bring the good name of the school in the life of society at large. Achievement is the key to the success of an educational institution. Achievement must be maintained or must be improved so that schools become stronger and more qualified so that they are in demand by education stakeholders. This condition will make students feel they have readiness (the ability to compete) in improving themselves in the learning process. The spirit of achievement possessed by students will have an impact on improving the quality of self and institutions in the Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School.

The value of worship is essentially the realization of the values of the teachings of Islam as a tradition in the behavior and culture of the school organization which is followed by all school members. Internalization of worship values developed at Islamic Elementary School is closely related to habituation of students to say greetings to fellow peers at school and to teachers, habituation to pray before and after learning in class, reading Al-Qur'an every day at school, memorizing short letters, performing duha prayers and praying in congregation at school.

Attention to this quality is a commitment developed in an institution driven by the principal as a leader. Quality is an advantage that must be achieved by schools. Effective schools are schools that are successful in learning and can adjust between quality and fairness standards. Quality refers to the high performance of students. The intended justice is

related to not differentiate between gender, economic and social status, ethnicity, and so on.

Dare to try and never give up is one of the values taught to students of Islamic Elementary School. This value contains an element of fighting spirit to achieve achievement in the whole learning process at school. Students must dare to face challenges and try to solve these challenges properly. Students dare to try to solve the challenges faced and never give up both in the learning process in the classroom and outside the classroom. This courage and the value of giving up are the foundation that students must-have in every learning process in school to be able to obtain the knowledge, experience, and skills needed by students for a better future.

Self-motivation is an intrinsic value developed to actualize students' self to achieve good performance in the learning process at school. This culture must be developed based on values that are relevant to the spirit of the school's vision and especially the alignment to the learning process as the primary mission of the school.

The strategy of developing a religious culture in shaping the nation's character of students at Al-GhontoryIslamic Elementary School can be implemented with the following steps: (a) it starts with the socialization of policies that have been formulated in a participatory manner to all students and the community. This socialization was

carried out by the principal together with the teacher to all school residents, (b) form teamwork to carry out programs to strengthen religious culture in schools so that they can be carried out properly. Team Work as a motivator in strengthening this religious culture has a very important position in its implementation, (c) practicing and getting used to running the core values of Islamic teachings to students in daily life at school as a manifestation of the learning process based on Islamic teachings, (d) give a good example to students in all learning activities held at school continuously by the guidance and teachings of Islam, (e) every weekend an evaluation of the process has been carried out to obtain feedback about the obstacles that arise and efforts to resolve them.

Strengthening religious culture is essential in developing educational institutions because culture will affect the performance and effectiveness of educational institutions. Thus, a strong and conducive religious culture must be formed and developed by the school principal and staff and teachers to optimally achieve the vision and mission of the school which is realized in the formation of the nation's character of students and improving the quality of education in schools. The strategy of strengthening religious culture in Al-GhontoryIslamic Elementary School is implemented by: (1) creating commitment, (2) Building effective communication, and (3) continuous improvement. This strategy can be seen in the form of an image as follows:

Fig. 2: Strategies for Developing Religious Culture in Shaping the Nation's Character of Students

Character education in Islamic elementary schools is not just about teaching what is right and what is wrong. More than that, character education instills habits about national character values so that students become aware of right and wrong behavior, able to understand good values , and are used to doing them. In other words, character education must involve not only the aspects of "good

knowledge (morality), but also" feeling well or loving good (moral feeling), and good behavior (moral action). This can be implemented by teaching religious values to students so they have an understanding and can implement it well in everyday life. The results of data analysis on the strategy of developing a religious culture in shaping the character of students can be explained in the form of a table as follows:

Strategies for Implementing Religious Culture				
Indicator	Score			Criteria
	F	N	(%)	
Commitment	70	80	88%	Very good
Communication	72	80	90%	Very good
Continual improvement	69	80	86%	Very good
Average Total Score	211	240	88%	Very good

Table 2: Strategies for Implementing Religious Culture in Shaping Student Character in Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School

Commitment to shape the national character of students must continue to be improved so that the formation of that character can be achieved properly. Commitment to carrying out quality learning tasks continues to be increased by the principal along with the teacher. In this case, the school principal always motivates performance continuously so that the commitment that has been built in the formation of the nation's character of students in the Islamic Elementary School can be run properly. Based on the results of the study showed that the commitment of all the academic community is 88% or in very good condition.

Communication is an effective means of developing a religious culture in schools, in this case, the headmaster builds a good communication system between teachers, staff, students, stakeholders, and the community. Communication as a means to develop and establish cooperation in improving the quality of education. Communication is also a vehicle for carrying out effective learning processes in schools and can be used in shaping the national character of students. The communication system at Islamic Elementary School is in very good condition or 90% of the receptors say very well so that the information channel can run well to all members of the organization. Problems that arise in education and learning can soon be resolved, because of a good communication system between the principal, teachers, and staff.

Efforts to make improvements carried out continuously in line with the education and learning processes that exist at the Al-Ghontory Islamic Elementary School. Improvements carried out are always based on evaluating learning programs implemented by the school. The evaluation is carried out every weekend and at that time feedback can be obtained to make improvements in the learning process so that the expected character education and quality of education will become a reality. The condition of continuous improvement based on information

from respondents is in very good condition or as much as 86% of the recipes stated very well.

Improvements are carried out continuously without the word stop. Character education and education quality must be improved to be better and quality concerning continuous improvement. Continuous improvement enables schools to monitor work processes and identify their strengths, opportunities that must be achieved, and challenges and obstacles that must be faced in improving the quality of education.

Continuous improvement always provides an opportunity for schools to continuously evaluate the work process that refers to strengthening religious culture in shaping the national character of students. This is because in the implementation of empowerment programs in schools there are still: (1) space to make improvements in every process of strengthening the religious culture in shaping the character of students, (2) every improvement, both large and small, remains valuable, (3) Small improvements complete meaningful changes, (4) mistakes are seen as opportunities for improvement, (5) everyone has the same responsibility to try to prevent problems from arising and to solve problems that arise, (6) everyone in the school and users The school is committed to improving school programs or schools on an ongoing basis to be able to shape the competencies and character of students.

The competence and formation of the nation's character of students in the Islamic Elementary School always emphasize the learning process on the abilities that must be possessed by students as well as the morality that must be possessed by students in actualizing religious values or the practices of Islamic teachings in daily life. day. The implementation of the assessment and control can be seen in the form of a picture as follows:

Fig. 3: Evaluation and Control Systems in Shaping Student Character in Islamic Elementary School

Based on the picture above, an explanation can be given that the evaluation and control system in the implementation of character education in Islamic Elementary Schools is carried out using authentic assessment techniques. This technique is carried out by the teacher by carrying out continuous observation of student behavior in internalizing religious values and student learning activities in the classroom and outside the classroom, assigning tasks to students both in the learning process in class and assignments that must be done in-home, active student participation in participating in the entire learning process in class, portfolio, and learning achievement tests on each competency that has been learned by students.

The results of evaluations conducted by teachers are used as a basis for improving the behavior and competencies of students who have not met the minimum standards that have been set previously. This improvement is carried out by the teacher by providing coaching and remedial teaching for students who have not yet achieved the competencies they expect. As for students who already meet the expected competencies, enrichment is held to strengthen and enhance students' understanding or competence so that the learning process can run effectively. This is carried out in an ongoing manner throughout the entire learning process in shaping the nation's character of students in school. An authentic assessment can be used as a teacher as a tool to control the quality of learning, competence, and national character of students in the whole learning process at Islamic Elementary School.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Schools as educational institutions are organizations that have several elements contained in the education system, namely: goals, personnel, facilities, and management activities. Schools will become more qualified if they have clear goals, good personnel, adequate facilities, a conducive climate and organizational culture, and effective management activities. This is because the culture and climate of the organization will have a strong influence on the performance of individuals and organizations beyond the system, structure, strategy, equipment, and so on.

A positive school organization culture can also influence the implementation of high-quality education and the formation of positive attitudes and morals for all personal in educational institutions. Such conditions are very supportive of achieving high learning achievement (DeRoche, 1985). Educational administration and management experts since the 1980s firmly put the principal's responsibility as the creator of school culture including conducive religious culture and characteristics of effective schools (Lipham, Rankin, & Hoeh, 1985). DeRoche (1985) asserted that the principal had the primary responsibility for structuring the culture of the school organization. This shows that the principal plays a very decisive role in creating success in school.

The implementation of character education needs to pay attention to the commitment and good example of the principal, teachers, and the center of education. Romanowski (2005) explains that character education is

more effective for students with good examples, modeled, and strengthened by schools and teachers. On the other hand, O'Sullivan (2004) explains that the easiest way to promote character education is to use a literature study because the story serves as a role model that connects experience and morals (Sanchez & Stewart, 2006). This was also carried out in Islamic elementary schools that taught character values based on the example of the Prophet Muhammad and his companions which were used as a source of student character learning. In this case, Revell and Arthur (2007) explain that teacher attitudes towards moral education also have an important role in the process of character education in schools.

Religious culture in shaping the national character of students contains the values of excellence that are developed in achieving the goals set. The results of Gordon, Mondy, Sharplin, & Premeaux (1990), Creemers & Reynolds (2002) show that a strong culture makes members more satisfied, motivated, and has a great commitment to the organization. Likewise, Sergiovanni (1987) found that a strong culture would increase the commitment, enthusiasm, and loyalty of members towards the organization. From these results, it can be concluded that a strong and positive religious culture will be able to shape the character of students according to the religious values taught in school.

School as an educational organization has its effectiveness and culture that forms the style of a whole and a unique system. The particularity of school culture is inseparable from the vision and the ongoing educational process that demands the existence of elements or components of the school as an area of organizational work. These elements interact with each other and reciprocally have links to each other, both artifacts and values, within the organization itself and with the external environment. Susanto (1997) suggests the following elements of organizational culture: (a) business environment: the organization has its business environment, and in practice must pay attention to customers, technology, competition, quality, stakeholders, and other factors that can support business success, (b) values; value is the idealization of one's ideals. As an ideal, it is certainly desirable, expected, and desirable. The value of the organization must be upheld by each of its members because it will determine the behavior displayed. These kinds of values such as honesty, empowerment, sincerity, worship, and so on, (c) Heroism; the existence of an organization is inseparable from the philosophy and goals of its founders. The founders and leaders of the organization have a large role that helps determine, shape, and instill cultural values that will be used as a reference for each member. The founders and leaders of the organization are obliged to socialize these values to all members, as well as being role models in their attitudes and actions, (d) Ceremony/procedure; ceremonies in an organization are natural, but special ways that reflect organizational culture can be formed to foster discipline or express gratitude for a successor to foster the pride of each member of his organization. Ceremonies can be performed to commemorate religious holidays, the success of members in achieving achievements, or to prevent informal gathering, (e) network; at present, the existence of a network can

determine success. The network was formed to strengthen the organization's existence, and also to facilitate various businesses. Through network formation, business engineering that is packaged in all solid communication can facilitate, facilitate, expand, socialize, and strengthen the organizational position.

Organizational culture in schools must be developed based on values that are relevant to the spirit of the school's vision and especially the alignment to the learning process as the primary mission of the school. Therefore, the core values (basic values) of schools must be directed at providing optimal learning services for students so that they can develop their potential optimally. Peter and Waterman as quoted by Hanson (1979) find values that are consistently implemented in good schools. These values include quality and service are the things that must be prioritized, always strive to be the best, give full attention to things that seem trivial (details), do not distance yourself from clients, do things as possible, work through people (not just cooperating / ordering), spurring innovation and tolerance for unsuccessful ventures.

Strategies for developing an effective school organization culture at Islamic Elementary School are implemented by (1) forming team-work, this team-work serves as the prime mover and pioneer in carrying out all the policies made by the school principal, (2) building effective communication with teachers, staff, and students. This communication system is run well in each school with the aim of creating a good and conducive school climate, (3) building a shared commitment with teachers, staff, students, stakeholders, and the community to create quality school institutions. This commitment is important to be realized as a joint responsibility in educating the nation. Quality schools must be created a shared commitment to always create creativity and innovation in improving the quality of education, (4) habituation to live the values developed by the school. This habituation is carried out with a good example of the principal, teachers, and staff.

In the context of creating a conducive culture in schools, education administration and management experts since the 1980s explicitly put the principal's responsibility as the creator of conducive school culture and characteristics of effective schools (Lipham, Rankin, & Hoeh, 1985; Davis, & Thomas, 1989) DeRoche (1985) asserts that the principal has the primary responsibility for structuring organizational culture and school climate, this shows that the principal plays a very decisive role in creating success in school.

The results of the study reinforce and develop previous research findings primarily related to the formation and development of organizational culture. At the beginning of its appearance, organizational culture refers to the vision of its founder which is influenced by internal ideals and external demands that exist within the scope of the organization. Therefore, in examining the formation process and organizational culture development strategy, it cannot be separated from the group process. Also, the process of the emergence of organizational culture takes quite a long time, and generally involves a figure (top manager) who

introduces the vision and mission to his staff, then referred by all group members.

These findings also reinforce the findings of Robbins (2001) explaining that: "The original culture is derived from the founder of philosophy. This, in turn, strongly influences the criteria used in hiring. The actions of the current top management set the general climate of what is acceptable behavior and what is not. How employees are to be socialized will depend on both the degree of success achieved in matching new employee's values to those of the organization's in the selection process on top management's preference for socialization methods "

Based on the above quotation it can be explained that organizational culture is formed departing from the philosophy possessed by the founder of the organization, then the organizational culture is used as a criterion in carrying out the actuating function in the organizational system. The actions of the top leadership in determining the general climate of behavior are acceptable and not. This is very important in efforts to create and develop an organizational culture that can help in improving the quality of education. A strong and dynamic organizational culture must be developed using the active role of top leaders in socializing the values that exist in the organization and the ability of leaders to influence and move all members of the organization to be able to carry out their duties properly.

Therefore, the values (basic values) of schools must be directed at providing optimal learning services for students so that they can develop their potential optimally. Peter and Waterman, as quoted by Hanson (1979), found values that were consistently implemented in good schools. These values include quality and service are things that must be prioritized, always strive to be the best, give full attention to things that seem trivial (details), do not distance yourself from students, do things as well as possible, work through people (not just working together to govern it), spurring innovation and tolerance for unsuccessful ventures.

The findings of this study provide support for the results of previous studies that show that commitment has a very large contribution in improving performance, achieving goals, showing better results (Supiyanto, 2015; Mutohar&Trisnantari, 2020). Commitment has implications for the morale and performance of school principals, teachers, and staff in realizing quality schools. In this case, everyone will support and strive to improve the quality of performance because they have a high commitment (Chen, Hsu, Tung, & Lee, 2010; Jackson, Gucciardi, Hodge, & Dimmock, 2016; Prasad & Jain, 2011). This commitment is very important to be commenced by all academicians in preparing quality human resources in the education and learning system in schools. Commitments and quality initiatives carried out will change the culture that causes school organizations to change the way they work by referring to the quality initiatives they carry out (Abdul-Samad, 2010; Vianello et al., 2011). The hope of this is that students will be able to implement the character values developed in schools and can also improve their learning achievement well.

The purpose and benefits of this communication are as a means to (1) improve managerial skills and social relations, (2) convey and or receive information, (3) convey and answer questions, (4) change behavior (thinking patterns, feelings, and actions) through planning, organizing, directing, and controlling, (5) changing social conditions, (6) two things that can change social behavior and conditions are communication and decision making (Usman, 2012).

Evaluation of character education is carried out in schools to determine the success of character education programs that have been implemented in schools. Evaluations in character education are carried out using authentic assessments. The authentic assessment focuses on the competence that is set to determine the true abilities possessed by students (Boud, 1995; Newmann & Associates, 1996). This assessment is to find out the real situation between the process and practice that occurs professionally (Gulikers et al., 2004; Messick, 1994). Authentic assessment is expected to stimulate students to develop their skills or competencies to the maximum.

Authentic assessment can be carried out by the teacher by observing student activity, abilities possessed by students, as well as through the completion of assignments, and portfolios. Segers, Dochy, and Cascallar (2003) argue that several aspects used in valuation can support the implementation of authentic assessments. The literature on authentic learning (Newmann & Associates, 1996; Wiggins, 1993), as well as the professional development and assessment literature (Boshuizen et al, 2004; Segers et al., 2003), explain that schools need to provide students authentic real learning. A learning experience that lives with the complexities of education and learning can stimulate students towards higher original thought processes and active learning. To encourage authentic learning and improve student learning achievement, authentic assessment can be carried out by authentic teaching to meet real-world expectations (Achieve, 2006; Biggs, 1996; Linn et al., 2002).

V. IMPLICATIONS

A. Theoretical Implications

The findings of this study have theoretical implications to shape the character of students in elementary school. The formation of student characters in primary schools needs to be made in the design of character education, the implementation of character education strategies, and evaluation systems in character education. Changes and developments in science and technology are accelerating in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, demanding educational institutions in elementary schools to prepare students to have the character of the nation and be able to face the era of change and development. Character education is implemented in preparing students to be able to play an active role in the development of science and technology and to have a good national character in the global era.

Commitment and role models have a very important role in character education. This finding reinforces the research results of Romanowski's (2005) which confirms

that the examples and models provided by teachers become more effective in character education in schools. Likewise, Arthur (2007) explains that teacher attitudes towards moral education also have an important role in the process of character education in schools. Research findings on the application of religious culture in shaping the national character of students can work well in realizing effective schools. The results of this study reinforce the findings of Gordon, Mondy, Sharplin, & Premeaux (1990), Creemers & Reynolds (2002) who explain that a strong culture makes members more satisfied, motivated, and have a great commitment to the organization.

B. Practical Implications

The findings of research on the design, implementation, and evaluation system of the development of religious culture in shaping the national character of students in primary schools bring to the practical implications that can be implemented by every elementary school in shaping the national character of students. Character education is carried out based on plans that have been prepared in the school curriculum with an appropriate implementation strategy and commitment of the entire academic community to realize it well. In order for the character education program to be run well, it is necessary to have an ongoing evaluation and control in the whole learning process at school. Authentic assessment can be used to find out the success of character education programs in schools. This shows that schools must be able to manage character education properly and appropriately so that it can be carried out effectively and efficiently.

VI. CONCLUSION

The goal of education is not only intelligence, knowledge, and knowledge, but also morals, character, character, values, behavior, mentality, and personality that are tough, superior and noble, which are called characters. To meet these expectations, a character education program was formulated that was integrated with the spirit of nationalism. This character education program can be implemented by developing a religious culture in schools in instilling the nation's character values of students. Religious culture in schools can influence the implementation of high-quality education and the formation of positive attitudes and morals for all personnel in educational institutions. This condition strongly supports the achievement of high learning achievement and the formation of the nation's character of students. This is due to the strong and effective school culture that can move all school personnel to improve morale and the quality of learning which has implications for improving the quality of education. Religious culture in a strong school will have a positive impact on the performance of institutions in general because the culture will direct the behavior of employees and organizational management. A well-preserved religious culture capable of displaying faith, pious, creative, and innovative behavior.

The benefits that can be drawn from this culture are that it can guarantee work results with better quality, open all communication networks, openness, togetherness, cooperation, kinship, find faults and quickly improve,

quickly adjust to developments outside. An effective religious culture is the values, beliefs, and actions as a result of a mutual agreement to practice the teachings of Islam to give birth to the commitment of all personnel to carry out consistently and consistently. Strong religious culture can also affect the implementation of high-quality education and the formation of positive attitudes and morals for all personnel in educational institutions. Such conditions are very supportive of achieving high learning achievement and character students.

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